

QoE Provisioning over mobile networks: The CASPER perspective

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Abstract—This paper highlights the vision of CASPER project towards user-centric network and service management in future mobile networks. Putting the end-users of the network at the epicenter of the service provisioning process, CASPER builds on top of the Software Defined Networking (SDN) and the Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) advances a middleware architecture which will realize user-centric orchestration of service and network functions. User centricity will be leveraged through a Quality of Experience- oriented framework, composed of three modular functions, namely the QoE monitoring and estimation, the QoE service and network management, and the QoE control interface.

Keywords—*Quality of Experience; Software Defined Networking; Network Function Virtualisation; Key performance indicators;*

I. INTRODUCTION

The future of mobile communications is likely to be very different to that which we are used to today. While demand for mobile broadband will continue to increase, largely driven by ultra-high definition video, we are already seeing the growing impact of technology in our everyday life as the things around us become ever more connected. The ITU name for the next generation technology is IMT-2020. It is well recognised as 5G.

5G will not only be an evolution of mobile broadband networks. It will bring new unique network and service capabilities. Firstly, it will ensure user experience continuity in challenging situations such as high mobility (e.g. in trains), very dense or sparsely populated areas, and journeys covered by heterogeneous technologies. In addition, 5G will be a key enabler for the Internet of Things by providing a platform to connect a massive number of sensors, rendering devices and actuators with stringent energy and transmission constraints. Furthermore, mission critical services requiring very high reliability, global coverage and/or very low latency, which are up to now handled by specific networks, typically public safety, will become natively supported by the 5G infrastructure.

5G will integrate networking, computing and storage resources into one programmable and unified infrastructure. This unification will allow for an optimised and more dynamic usage of all distributed resources, and the convergence of fixed, mobile and broadcast services. In addition, 5G will support multi tenancy models, enabling operators and other players to collaborate in new ways.

Leveraging on the characteristic of current cloud computing, 5G will push the single digital market further, paving the way for virtual pan European operators relying on nationwide infrastructures. 5G will be designed to be a sustainable and scalable technology. Firstly, the telecom industry will compensate tremendous usage growth by drastic energy consumption reduction and energy harvesting. In addition, cost reduction through human task automation and hardware optimisation will enable sustainable business models for all ICT stakeholders.

Last but not least, 5G will create an ecosystem for technical and business innovation. Since network services will rely more and more on software, the creation and growth of startups in the sector will be encouraged.

Technologies such as the Software Defined Networking (SDN) [3], and the Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) [4] are already being deployed by operators and will continue to enable the move towards the hyper-connected society alongside developments in 5G. Considerable potential also remains for increasing 4G adoption in many countries, and we expect 4G network infrastructure to account for much of the \$1.7 trillion the world's mobile operators will invest between now and 2020. Operators will continue to focus on generating a return on investment from their 4G (and 3G) networks by developing new services and tariffing models that make most efficient use of them.

The current telecom infrastructure is expected to work with the 5G core network as it is backward compatible. But to deliver on 5G promises, current 2G/3G/4G networks will have to be upgraded, or probably replaced. New 5G RAN (Radio Access Network) architecture with new high frequency power amplifiers and new filters will be developed to handle the mmWave traffic processing which is needed to boost data throughput to maximum 20Gbps. This is needed in order to implement massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) or M2M, and provide connection density of one million devices per km², which are some of the promises of 5G.

Similarly, current devices can still work with pre-5G networks (3G or 4G), but new devices will have to be designed and developed to access and utilise the power of 5G. Even smart applications need to be updated, to cope with the updated smart device hardware, to handle the high speed flow of data within 5G. Neither device nor smart applications' vendors would accept to be the bottleneck in the 5G journey.

Considering the above analysis, the remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the CASPER vision towards the 5G era. Section III summarizes recent standardization activity, considered in CASPER middleware architecture designing process. Section IV and V illustrate the CASPER embraced technologies and the key scenarios for evaluation and testbed implementation, respectively. Section VI specifies service related key requirements and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the adopted scenarios. Section VII moves from the service perspective to user-centricity and describes the CASPER framework over the architecture that will realize QoE provisioning over mobile networks. Section VIII concludes the paper.

II. THE CASPER'S PERSPECTIVE

The current paradigm in service provisioning lacks thorough end-to-end interpretation from the quality viewpoint, while the end-users'/customers' profiles and preferences are mostly not taken into account. The subjective perception of a provided service, depicted in the Quality of Experience (QoE) term [1][2], is one of the most important factors for a user's decision on retaining the service or giving it up, and the key parameter for enabling advanced customer experience management (CEM). The main objective of CASPER project¹ is to combine academic and industrial forces towards leveraging the expected benefits of QoE exploitation in 5G networks.

CASPER moves beyond theoretical analysis and focus on the applicability of research findings into an integrated middleware architecture, following industrial requirements and recent standardization activity. The user-centric logic of the CASPER project is based on a deep analysis of the QoE, adopted mainly by the works in [5][6][7][8], combined with the flexibility and re-configurability provided by the SDN/NFV technology in a bidirectional manner to acquire QoE influence factors from anchor points in the network and to apply QoE-driven network and service management policies.

Three interlinked modules will be implemented, one-to-one mapped to the three instrumental functionalities required for the beneficial intervention of QoE in network and service management:

- Reliable and passive QoE monitoring, including adaptive and objective QoE estimation mechanisms;
- Robust and real-time QoE-driven service management and CEM policies;
- Efficient QoE controller to realize the interface between the middleware and the network functions.

The instrumental modules of CASPER will be integrated and optimized in a single solid solution that facilitates the following twofold long-term target:

- Customize service delivery through acquiring and combining knowledge available in distributed places, such as various network elements in the access/backhaul/core network, as well as in databases, human subjects and surrounding environments.

¹CASPER is a H2020-MSCA-RISE project (grant 645393), started in January 2016.

- Motivate service providers to use enhanced QoE-driven service management techniques as well as advanced CEM policies by exploiting the potentialities of SDN/NFV technologies.

III. RECENT STANDARDISATION ACTIVITY

In the domain of service quality, different mechanisms have been standardised depending on the wireless communication system. Focusing on Long Term Evolution (LTE) networks, 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) has standardised different bearers for differentiated treatment of the provided services, while traffic flows are separated by using Quality of Service (QoS) class identifiers (QCI) and allocation and retention priorities (ARP) [9]. Moving to the domain of QoE provisioning, the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) has defined QoE requirements for multimedia services [10]. In their attempt to reduce vendor lock up and time to market of new services while maintaining high QoE, communication service providers have initiated the ETSI Network Functions Virtualisation Group. NFV in combination with SDN can provide unparalleled real-time control over an operator's network. Based on the ETSI GS NFV 002 Architectural Framework [11], a new network layer is defined, named NFV Management and Orchestration, which is expected to provide intelligent control over all physical and virtualised network elements. Furthermore, a lot of work in real time calculation of key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and metrics for measuring QoE using Big Data tools is taking place. The Tele-Management (TM) Forum has released TR202 [12] with a reference Big Data Architecture as well as a list of KPIs related to network QoE and other metrics. Building on TM Forum's metrics, and with the advent of SDN/NFV, industrial research aims at a closed-loop feedback control, where the system automatically will make small adjustments to the network while simultaneously measuring the impact of these adjustments. Thus, the network of the future will react autonomously to any foreseeable and unforeseeable conditions.

IV. EMBRACED TECHNOLOGIES

The proposed middleware incorporates a QoE orchestrator on top of SDN/NFV tools such as OpenStack, OpenDay Light and the OpenFlow protocol [3].

The main purpose will be to interact with the end-user and to self-configure and optimize in terms of locally available functionalities. For instance, upon recognition of a silver-age user, the local service management block could produce an indicative message to the application or other device software for self-configuring, if this functionality is supported. The fonts may be enlarged, the screen light may be increased, some help suggestions may pop-up on the screen more often, etc. Another example is the selection of a less transmission-power harvesting network, when the user terminal has low battery (e.g., switch to Wi-Fi for browsing instead of using the cellular network, especially if the user is at the cell-edge). Additionally, with the help of industrial beneficiaries, any proposed solution will consider the applicability and device constraints, towards

developing QoE functions that can be directly applied to the current smart mobile devices.

More specifically, the ETSI NFV reference architecture [4] will provide the required functionality for QoE-driven service configuration in the network plane. Based on this architecture, future virtualized networks can provide a bi-directional closed-loop feedback environment that, for the first time, can permit the implementation of systems that act autonomously in order to maintain high levels of QoE with minimal human intervention.

With respect to the network plane, the evaluation of the customers' QoE score is a huge asset that may be used not only for marketing and advertisement purposes, but also as a way to reduce customer churn (CEM procedures). Moreover, by using this information, the operator will have the power to perform more effective network and customer database management, optimize the network, improve the user experience and offer personalized services and quality to its customers. Such personalized quality of delivery will be performed with the aid of NFV control functions, on the top of different network devices at the access and the core network. In CASPER, innovative service management policies will be designed using as input the estimated personalized QoE value acquired by the estimation phase, together with the transaction profile under consideration and available information about the key influence indicators per transaction profile. More specifically, the use of SDN techniques will be examined towards isolating the control plane from the data plane, and allowing for a virtualized grouping and controlling of the communication sessions according to rules related to the transaction profiles that they belong to.

V. TARGETED SCENARIOS

A. Scenario A: Real-time communication between two parties

The first scenario includes any type of real-time communication between two parties, directly via the infrastructure of the MNO or ISP. The involved users have connectivity to the same or different operators (intra-operator and inter-operator cases, respectively) and they may be located in the same or different cells. This scenario is presented in Fig.1.

The main application to be studied here is *Voice over IP* (VoIP), but also Short Message Service (SMS) or video calls fall into the same scenario.

Although video constitutes the majority of traffic nowadays, voice calls continue to be a dominant service used by everyone in a daily basis. In contrast to video, which is mainly associated to leisure browsing, voice calls may imply business or safety use cases. Thus, it remains critical, in a challenging packet-based era to provide excellent quality for voice calls. A great challenge is therefore the comprehension of QoE KPIs for voice calls, as well as the guaranteeing of excellent QoE under challenging network conditions or high congestion. Moreover, if multiple MNO/ISPs are involved, issues arise regarding liability in case of low QoE. The question for CASPER is how the technologies of NFV/SDN can be used for improving the voice experience of a mobile user, especially in a highly

congested network or challenging network conditions (e.g., cell-edge user, etc.).

Fig.1 Scenario A

Fig.2 Scenario B

Fig.3 Scenario C

B. Scenario B: Multimedia content delivery from a service provider

This scenario mainly concerns cases of video content delivery, namely video streaming. The common paradigm nowadays is that OTT parties provide access to video streaming services, which the users are able to access only through their MNO or ISP connection. (Note that MNOs or ISPs may also provide

video streaming services by themselves to their subscribers.) The second scenario of CASPER is presented in Fig. 2.

The main applications that are going to be studied here are:

- Non-adaptive video streaming (non real-time service)
- HTTP Adaptive Streaming (non real-time service)
- Live TV / IPTV (real-time service)

The major challenges in this category of scenarios stems from the fact that the video content is usually made available by an OTT provider, whereas it is delivered by a traditional MNO/ISP. Therefore, QoS/QoE guarantees from the OTT side are mostly absent, and are mainly oriented to providing a high-resolution video content to the viewers. However, the delivery procedure of the content itself is in the discretion of the MNO/ISP. Only specific agreements between OTTs and MNO/ISPs can provide some kind of assurance regarding the quality of the delivered video, but these mainly concern the location of OTT video servers being close to critical points of the MNO/ISP infrastructure. However, other than that, no dynamic and on-demand control is feasible. Consequently, if the quality of the offered video is bad despite the OTT’s proactive measures, the problem cause and potential solution are out of his reach.

A second challenge in these type of scenarios is the translation of QoS guarantees to QoE MOS and KPIs’ satisfaction, since QoE is the major metric for evaluating the quality of a multimedia service.

C. Scenario C: Real-time communication among multiple parties via an intermediate server

The third category of scenarios is the most challenging one since it includes an OTT provider, one or more MNO/ISP providers and multiple users. Applications that fall into this category are Skype calls (voice or video), Viber, gaming, and teleconference, among others. The traffic in this case is accumulated at a server in the possession of the OTT party, passing however through the network infrastructure of one or more MNO/ISPs (intra-operator and inter-operator case, respectively). This scenario is presented in Fig. 3.

The challenges in this case include the ones discussed in the previous two scenarios, as well as the fact that this one involves multimedia content delivery. A major challenging issue from a QoE perspective is also that proper and reliable QoE estimation models for these types of applications are not available yet, and finding appropriate KPIs is not a trivial issue. QoE monitoring is a challenging topic too, since information from the OTT, MNO/ISP, and user need to be jointly collected and processed. The CASPER middleware architecture will tackle these challenges by providing interfaces to all involved parties for the purposes of QoE monitoring as well as management. It will therefore serve as a platform that enables interactions among the different stakeholders, with the target of providing user-personalized, application-aware and context-aware QoE improvements.

VI. REQUIREMENTS AND KPIs PER SCENARIO

This section presents and analyze the KPIs related to QoE functions. The most important KPIs for the end-users’ QoE are depicted in Table I [5].

The improvement of one or more of these parameters indicates that QoE will be also improved, and thus, network engineering targeted on these factors should be conducted. In parallel, the values of these KPIs represent an indication of whether the network delivery (e.g., KPI: delay) or the experience of the user (e.g., KPI: number of stalling events) are good or not. Overall, these KPIs can be seen as:

- QoE influence factors
- Indicators of the quality of the user experience

KPIs will be used as a “common vocabulary” for describing the effectiveness of the service delivery for the use cases investigated. Any proposed algorithms by CASPER will be tested against these KPIs, depicting their potential improvement.

TABLE I. MOST IMPORTANT KPIs PER SCENARIO

Scenario	Most important (service-dependent) KPIs
Scenario A	Packet loss ratio, Delay, Jitter, Codec, Coding rate
Scenario B	Data rate, Video bit rate, Media bit rate, Number of stalling events, Duration of stalling events, Initial delay, Video start failure, Time on highest layer, Frequency of quality switches, Amplitude of quality switches
Scenario C	Frame rate, Image quality, Video resolution, Packet loss ratio for audio and video packets, Relative delay between video and audio packets, Data rate
All scenarios	QoE, Throughput / Goodput, SINR, Outage probability, Network overhead, Spectral efficiency, Battery consumption, Cost

VII. KEY ARCHITECTURAL ENTITIES

In CASPER we have identified three main building blocks, namely the *QoE-Controller*, *QoE-Monitor* and *QoE-Manager*, that are required towards introducing QoE in mobile networks of the 5G era.

QoE-Controller. Actually, it is the interface between the central entity and the underlying network. It performs the exchange of information in both directions. More specifically, it requests and collects feedback from appropriate data sources (arrows (1) and (2) in Fig.4) and it applies any QoE-aware control decisions back to the network (arrow (6) in Fig.4). It also provides input of interest both to the QoE-Monitor and the QoE-Manager (arrows (3a) and (3b) in Fig. 4). In the communication with the QoE-Monitor, the QoE-Controller offers QoE-input data on a per flow basis, while in the communication with the QoE-Manager, it sends information regarding the current network state (e.g., availability of resources, performance statistics etc.).

QoE-Monitor. This building block performs the estimation of the QoE and reports the results to the QoE-Manager (arrow (4)

in Fig.4). To be more precise, the QoE-Monitor initially performs traffic classification using statistical analysis [13] to deduce the type of traffic of the considered flow. Then, it exploits built-in QoE assessment functions a.k.a QoE estimation models. Depending on the identified traffic type, the proper QoE estimation model is selected, followed by an estimation of the QoE. It needs to be noted, that all available QoE models can be integrated offline into the QoE-Monitor by the operators, namely during the design phase of the central QoE management entity and prior to its real-time operation, which makes the original selection of QoE models very crucial.

QoE-Manager. This entity is responsible for conducting any type of CEM (arrow (5a) in Fig. 4) or QoE-aware network management (arrow (5b) in Fig. 4). It exploits input from the QoE-Controller regarding the current network state and estimated QoE scores from the QoE-Monitor. Additionally, it considers network policies or Service Level Agreements to decide and command measures that need to be imposed to the network for solving quality problems at hand. Decisions can be taken per flow or catholically, respecting user policies (e.g., subscription profile, charging information, etc.) and current network constraints (e.g., availability in resources). As mentioned in the description of the QoE-Controller entity, the adaptation/control actions that realize these decisions are applied to the network through the QoE-Controller. However, the QoE-Manager is in charge of actualizing based on the underlying network type.

Fig.4 Required functionalities for QoE-based service provisioning

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

The new era of service provisioning requires brave steps beyond the current rigid architecture where network operators and service providers ignore the way that their customers perceive the provided services. CASPER project visions a user centric orchestration, joint for network and service management, enabled by the SDN and NFV technologies. The current paper describes meaningful scenarios where this orchestration can be proven beneficial and highlights the critical functions required to realize it.

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